

ISic4334

I.Sicily inscription 4334

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material**Object****Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Corleone

Provenance

only known from copy in MS in Biblioteca Civica di Palermo

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 61.0741

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.525

Rizzone, V.G. 2011. Opus Christi edificabit: stati e funzioni dei cristiani di Sicilia attraverso l'apporto dell'epigrafia (secoli IV-VI). *Documenti e studi di Synaxis* 25. Troina. At F17

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